

LEARNING IS THE BEST PRAYER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11664754>

ABSTRACT

More challenging is the effort to discern the origins and function of prayer. Some will argue that the impetus to pray comes from outside the person who prays; a divine or "cosmic" force inspires the act. Others will contend that the impulse arises purely from within the individual; it is fundamentally a form of self-talk. The stance adopted establishes the terms of investigation to be conducted and places limits around possible conclusions. This initial ambiguity is not resolvable by scientific researchers because their intellectual tools and conceptual language do not function effectively in this philosophical domain. Nonetheless, to sidestep these questions entirely is to miss the opportunity to systematically explore how these perspectives in and of themselves are amenable to scientific study.

Key phrases: "al-jama'a", "al-ghuraba", "sawadu-l-a'zam", "al-asar", "as-salaf", "al-hanifiya", "ahlu-l-hadith", "Ahlu-s-Sunnah wa-l-Jamaa"

When the era of digitization has reached a high level and the subjugation of the minds of the masses, especially the young generation, through cyberspace is at its peak, the struggle for human spiritual and educational views remains one of the most important issues. It can be seen that the current struggle for the above-mentioned spiritual and educational views in Islam, or rather one of the debates, revolves around the question of what is better, learning or jihad.

Islamic scholars consider both knowledge and Jihad as important actions. One of the remarkable aspects of the matter is that one of these two acts is "fard ayn" (individual obligation) and the other is "fard saqqah" (collective obligation). If we consider the analysis of this issue in short lines, we can come to the following points.

One of the questions that most Muslims often ask is: "Is Jihad a pillar of Islam?" The reason why such a question arises is that some scholars, taking into account the merits of Jihad, say that it is the sixth pillar of Islam, or the text of the hadith, which says "Jihad is the pinnacle of Islam", is incorrectly translated into the meaning "Jihad is the pillar of Islam", or a number of hadiths are incorrectly interpreted. It can be seen that it is understood. In fact, there are 5 pillars of Islam and they are listed in the famous Hadith of Gabriel ¹. A man asked Sahabah ibn Umar: "Aren't you going to participate in the military campaign?" he asked. Ibn Umar: "I heard from our Prophet (SAW) that Islam is built on 5 pillars..." ² and listed all the pillars. It is known from this hadith that Ibn Umar did not consider Jihad as a pillar of Islam based on the message given by the Prophet.

From the work cited by Ibn Umar, a number of scholars did not include Jihad in the pillars of Islam and said that it is obligatory. Qazi Iyad, the representative of the Maliki madhhab: "In

¹ Abu-l-Husayn Muslim ibn Hajjaj. Sahih Muslim. – Riyadh: Dor as-salam, 2000. – B.24

² Abu-l-Husayn Muslim ibn Hajjaj. Sahih Muslim. – Riyadh: Dor as-salam, 2000. – B.29

these words of Ibn Umar, there is evidence that Jihad is not obligatory and does not belong to the pillar of Islam!" In fact, Jihad is obligatory enough. ³Muhyiddin Nawawi, a representative of the Shafi'i sect, says: "Ibn Umar's words confirm that ghazawa (military campaign) is not a fard ayn, because there are 5 pillars of Islam and ghazawa is not one of them." ⁴Ibn Rajab, a representative of the Hanbali sect, says: "In the hadith narrated by Ibn Umar (regarding the pillars of Islam), Jihad is not mentioned as one of the best deeds, even though it is one of the best actions."⁵ In the hadith with the sentences *"Islam is the beginning of affairs, prayer is its pillar, and Jihad is its peak"*, it is mentioned that Jihad is not a pillar of Islam, but its peak. ⁶Ibn Rajab commented on this hadith: "Jihad is neither the beginning nor the pillar (pillar) of Islam, on which it is necessary to build, and this is due to two reasons: one - according to the opinion of most scholars, jihad is not obligatory like the pillars of Islam, but fard is sufficient; the other is that Jihad will not be carried out continuously until the Day of Judgment. After the death of Jesus, peace be upon him, there will be no religion other than Islam, and there will be no need for military action, and there will be no need for jihad. As for the pillars of Islam, they will remain as an obligation for every believer until the command of Allah (Doomsday). ⁷In addition, Ahlu-s-Sunna wa-l-Jama'a scholars believe that the type of jihad related to military action is fard sufficient, according to Surah Tawba in the Qur'an: " It is not necessary **for believers to go out into battle (battle). Doesn't one category emerge from each of their groups?! (The rest of them) learn religion** from the Prophet , and when their people **return to them (from battle), do they not warn them to avoid (sin)?!** They quote verse 122 as proof. There is an important point here. Jihad is carried out only under the leadership of, or at the behest of, an officially recognized leader, and not at the whims and mouths of individuals who proclaim themselves to be false leaders of the Muslims. Scholars cite the following hadith as a proof of this: *"Whoever obeys the emir has obeyed me, and whoever disobeys the emir has disobeyed me." Because the imam (the one who protects Muslims from the suffering of enemies and protects the unity of Islam) is a shield, and one fights (against the infidels) obeying his commands and actions and moves forward following him* ⁸. Scholars divide the type of jihad related to military operations into 2: one - if it is related to attack (warning); the second one is related to protection (for freedom), currently the first one is left out of practice (for a number of reasons, this issue is a topic for another study), it is said that basically 2 types are active.

The second part of the argument is that the acquisition of knowledge is the best form of worship. The Prophet Muhammad (SAW) himself said: *"The virtue of acquiring knowledge is more dear to me than the virtue of worship, and the best of religions is piety . "* ⁹Scholars cite the following hadith among the arguments that raise the importance of knowledge to the same

³ Abu-l-Fazl Iyad ibn Musa. Ikmalu-l-malum bi fawaidi-l-Muslim. – V:1. – Cairo: Dor al-wafa, 1998. – P.227.

⁴ Muhyiddin Abu Zakariya Nawawi. Sahih Muslim bi-sharhi-n-Nawawi. – V:1 – Cairo: al-Matbua'-l-Misriya bi-l-Azhariya, 1929. – P.179.

⁵ Zainuddin Abu-l-Faraj Abdurrahman ibn Shihobiddin ibn Rajab. Jamiu-l-uluvum wa-l-hikam. – Beirut: Dor Ibn Kathir, 2008. – P.129.

⁶ Abu Isa Muhammad ibn Isa Tirmidhi. Al-Jami'u-l-kabir. – V:4. – Beirut: Dar al-gharb al-islami, 1996. – P.363.

⁷ Zainuddin Abu-l-Faraj Abdurrahman ibn Shihobiddin ibn Rajab. Jamiu-l-uluvum wa-l-hikam. – Beirut: Dor Ibn Kathir, 2008. – P.130.

⁸ Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail Bukhari. Sahihu-l-Bukhari. - Damascus: Dor ibn Kathir, 2002. – P.729.

⁹ Jalaluddin ibn Abi Bakr Suyuti. Al-Jamiu'-s-saghir. - Beirut: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiya, 2004. – P.363.

level: "Requiring knowledge is obligatory for every Muslim." ¹⁰Sahaba Ali ibn Abu Talib says the following about learning: "A scholar is better than a fasting person, a person who performs the evening prayer, and a mujahid." ¹¹Tabein Jabir bin Zayd Azdi says: "One day I asked Ibn Abbas about Jihad, and he said to me: "Don't you want me to inform you about something better than Jihad?" said. Me: "Sure!" I said. He said to me: "Build a mosque and teach religious obligations, sunnah and jurisprudence there." ¹²Hasan Basri, one of the subjects, said: "The ink of scholars is heavier than the blood of martyrs." ¹³According to the pillars of Islam, there is no prayer better than Jihad. Ahmad ibn Hanbal's son Abdullah asked: "Where should a person who has 500 dirhams spend this money, for anger and Jihad, or for learning?" When asked, he replied: "If this person is without knowledge, it is more dear to me that he spends on knowledge." As proof of the superiority of knowledge over Jihad, scholars ¹⁴cite Surah ToHa, verse 114, **saying that Allah taught His Prophet to ask for an increase in knowledge, not Jihad. In addition, above Surah Tawba: " The believers do not have to go out to battle (battle)." Doesn't one category emerge from each of their groups?! (The rest of them) learn religion from the Prophet , and when their people return to them (from battle) , do they not warn them to avoid (sin) ?!** " In the sentences mentioned in verse 122, there is a call not to stop learning from the Prophet. Also, there are types of Jihad against the self and Satan (not related to military action), which is considered obligatory for every believer, but even in this case, scholars express an opinion that it is impossible to pass this stage without knowledge.

At the same time, one thing should not be forgotten, if the enemy attacks the land where Muslims live, then most of the scholars, instead of getting knowledge, defend their country with the call of the leader: "**O believers! What happened to you that when you are told to move in the way of God (against evil) , you put your weight on the ground (sit down) ?! Do you agree to the life of the world after the hereafter ? Compared to the Hereafter, the taste of this life is very little!** (Tawba, 38) they say that according to this verse, fard becomes obligatory and becomes more important. The reason is that every prayer (be it knowledge or Jihad) is performed on time.

From the information given above, it can be concluded that today, in the era of peace, stability and security in the country, the most important prayer for Muslims, especially young people, is to acquire knowledge.

References:

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¹⁰Ibn Maja . Sunan . – Cairo: Dor ihya al-kutub al-islamiya, 1954. – P.81.

¹¹ Abdu-l-Mo'min Khalaf Dimiyati. Al-Matjuru-r-rabih fi sawabi-l-amali-s-saleh. – Beirut: Maktaba va matbua'tu-n-nahdati-l-hadisa, 1994. - B.16.

¹² Ibn Abdu-l-Barr. Jame' bayani-l-ilm wa fazlhi. – V: 1. – Riyadh: Dor ibn Javzi, 1994. – P. 153.

¹³ Ismail ibn Muhammad Ajlunni. Kashfu-l-khafa and muzylu-l-ilbas. – V:2. – Cairo: Maktabat al-Qudsi, 1933.–P.200.

¹⁴ Abdullah Muhammad ibn Muflih Maqdisi. Al-Adabu-sh-sharia'. – V:2. – Beirut: Muassasatu-r-risala, 1999. – P.43.